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Star and Wheel on Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph with a Specific Type of Independency of SuperHyperVertices

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Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph; SuperHyper_{STABLE}; Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

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Article

Star and Wheel On Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With A Specific Type Of Independency of SuperHyperVertices

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Abstract: New ideas on the framework of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph for different styles of Neutrosophic SuperHyper-Wheel and Neutrosophic SuperHyper-Star are introduced. More instances and more clarifications alongside sufficient references are featured with a specific type of independency of SuperHyperVertices.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyper_{STABLE}, Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

MSC: 5C17, 05C22, 05E45

1. Scientific Research

Referred to Ref.[2].

Theorem 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V'} F(V_i))| \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) \mid \forall V_i \in V'', \forall V_j \in V'' : \\
 & T'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) \not\leq \min[T_V(V'_i), T_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}'} \\
 & I'_V(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) \not\leq \min[I_V(V'_i), I_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}'} \\
 & \text{and } F'_V(E_{i'})(V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}) \not\leq \min[F_V(V'_i), F_V(V'_j)]_{V'_i, V'_j \in E_{NSHG}} \\
 & \}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 1. Referred to the Figure 1.

Figure 1. Referred to the Example (1)

Theorem 2. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheelStyles-I don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.76, 0.76, 0.76) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \quad V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad \}
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 2. *Referred to the Figure 2.*

Figure 2. Referred to the Example (2)

Theorem 3. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheelStyles-II don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.73, 0.73, 0.73) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} |\{(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))\} \\
 & V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' : \\
 & T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \}
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 3. Referred to the Figure 3.

Figure 3. Referred to the Example (3)

Theorem 4. Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheelStyles-III don't coincide.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4}\}} T(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4}\}} I(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4}\}} F(V_i))| \\ & = (0.92, 0.92, 0.92) = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))|$$

$$V_{i=1,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$V_{i=1,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$V_2 \in V'', \forall V_3 \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) =$$

$$\min[T_{V'}(V_2), T_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2'}$$

$$I'_V(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) =$$

$$\min[I_{V'}(V_2), I_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2'}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) =$$

$$\min[F_{V'}(V_2), F_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2'}$$

$$V_2 \in V'', \forall V_4 \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) =$$

$$\min[T_{V'}(V_2), T_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2'}$$

$$I'_V(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) =$$

$$\min[I_{V'}(V_2), I_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2'}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) =$$

$$\min[F_{V'}(V_2), F_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2'}$$

$$V_4 \in V'', \forall V_3 \in V'' :$$

$$\begin{aligned} T'_{V'}(E_2) &= (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &= \min[T'_{V'}(V_4), T'_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2'} \\ I'_{V'}(E_2) &= (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &= \min[I'_{V'}(V_4), I'_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2'} \\ \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_2) &= (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &= \min[F'_{V'}(V_4), F'_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2'} \\ &\} \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 4. Referred to the Figure (4).

Figure 4. Referred to the Example (4)

Theorem 5. Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheelStyles-IV don't coincide.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4,7}\}} T(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4,7}\}} I(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4,7}\}} F(V_i))| \\ & = (1.15, 1.15, 1.15) = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))|$$

$$V_{i=1,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$V_{i=1,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$V_{i=7,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=7,3} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$V_{i=7,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=7,4} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_1 \in V'', \forall V_7 \in V'' : \\
&T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_1), T_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
&I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_1), I_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
&\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_1), F_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_2 \in V'', \forall V_3 \in V'' : \\
&T'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_2), T_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&I'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_2), I_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_2), F_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_2 \in V'', \forall V_4 \in V'' : \\
&T'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_2), T_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2}, \\
&I'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_2), I_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2}, \\
&\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_2), F_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_4 \in V'', \forall V_3 \in V'' : \\
&T'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_4), T_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&I'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_4), I_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_4), F_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&\}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Example 5. Referred to the Figure 5.

Figure 5. Referred to the Example (5)

Theorem 6. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheelStyles-V don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4,6-7}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4,6-7}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-4,6-7}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (1.39, 1.39, 1.39) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 & V_{i=1,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3} \in V'' : \\
 & T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
 & I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
 & \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
 & V_{i=1,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4} \in V'' : \\
 & T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
 & I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
 & \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=7,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=7,3} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=7,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=7,4} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=6,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=6,3} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_1 \in V'', \forall V_7 \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_1), T_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_1), I_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_1), F_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_1 \in V'', \forall V_6 \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_1), T_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_1), I_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_1), F_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_6 \in V'', \forall V_7 \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_1), T_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_1), I_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_1), F_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_2 \in V'', \forall V_3 \in V'' : \\
&T'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_2), T_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&I'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_2), I_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_2), F_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_2 \in V'', \forall V_4 \in V'' : \\
&T'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_2), T_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2}, \\
&I'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_2), I_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2}, \\
&\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_2), F_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_4 \in V'', \forall V_3 \in V'' : \\
&T'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_4), T_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&I'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_4), I_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_4), F_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&\}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Example 6. Referred to the Figure 6.

Figure 6. Referred to the Example (6)

Theorem 7. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheelStyles-VI don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-7}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-7}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-7}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (1.65, 1.65, 1.65) =
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))|$$

$$V_{i=1,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}$$

$$I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}$$

$$V_{i=1,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}$$

$$I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=1,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,5} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=7,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=7,3} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=7,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=7,5} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=2,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=2,5} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=7,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=7,4} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=6,3} \in V'', \forall V_{j=6,3} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_1 \in V'', \forall V_7 \in V'' : \\
&T'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_1), T_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
&I'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_1), I_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
&\text{and } F'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_1), F_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_1 \in V'', \forall V_6 \in V'' : \\
&T'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_1), T_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
&I'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_1), I_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
&\text{and } F'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_1), F_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_6 \in V'', \forall V_7 \in V'' : \\
&T'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_1), T_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
&I'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_1), I_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1}, \\
&\text{and } F'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_1), F_{V'}(V_7)]_{V_1, V_7 \in E_1},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_2 \in V'', \forall V_3 \in V'' : \\
&T'_V(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_2), T_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&I'_V(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_2), I_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
&\text{and } F'_V(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_2), F_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_2, V_3 \in E_2},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&V_2 \in V'', \forall V_4 \in V'' : \\
&T'_V(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_2), T_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2}, \\
&I'_V(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_2), I_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2}, \\
&\text{and } F'_V(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.19, 0.19, 0.19) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_2), F_{V'}(V_4)]_{V_2, V_4 \in E_2},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_4 \in V'', \forall V_3 \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_4), T_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_4), I_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_2) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_4), F_{V'}(V_3)]_{V_4, V_3 \in E_2},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_4 \in V'', \forall V_5 \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_4), T_{V'}(V_5)]_{V_4, V_5 \in E_3}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_4), I_{V'}(V_5)]_{V_4, V_5 \in E_3}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_4), F_{V'}(V_5)]_{V_4, V_5 \in E_3},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_4 \in V'', \forall V_6 \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_4), T_{V'}(V_6)]_{V_4, V_6 \in E_3}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_4), I_{V'}(V_6)]_{V_4, V_6 \in E_3}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.24, 0.24, 0.24) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_4), F_{V'}(V_6)]_{V_4, V_6 \in E_3},
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_6 \in V'', \forall V_5 \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_6), T_{V'}(V_5)]_{V_6, V_5 \in E_3}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_6), I_{V'}(V_5)]_{V_6, V_5 \in E_3}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_3) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_6), F_{V'}(V_5)]_{V_6, V_5 \in E_3}, \\
& \}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Example 7. Referred to the Figure 7.

Figure 7. Referred to the Example (7)

Theorem 8. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperStarStyles-I don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.78, 0.78, 0.78) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' : \\
 & T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k} \\
 & \}
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 8. *Referred to the Figure 8.*

Theorem 9. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperStarStyles-II don't coincide.*

Figure 8. Referred to the Example (8)

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & | \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5-6}\}} T(V_i), \right. \\
 & \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5-6}\}} I(V_i), \right. \\
 & \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3,5-6}\}} F(V_i) \right) | \\
 & = (1.01, 1.01, 1.01) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} | \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) | \\
 & \quad V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k} \\
 & \quad V_{i=3,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5-6} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=1,6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,6} \in V'' :
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
 &\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
 I'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
 &\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
 \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
 &\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
 &\}
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 9. Referred to the Figure 9.

Figure 9. Referred to the Example (9)

Theorem 10. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperStarStyles-III don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} T(V_i), \\
 &\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} I(V_i), \\
 &\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 &= (1.27, 1.27, 1.27) = \\
 &= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' : \\
& T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& V_{i=1,4,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4,5} \in V'' : \\
& T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& V_{i=3,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5-6} \in V'' : \\
& T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& V_{i=4,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=4,5-6} \in V'' : \\
& T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& V_{i=1,6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,6} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& T'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1'} \\
& I'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1'} \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
& V_{i=3,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,4} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& T'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1'} \\
& I'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1'} \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
& \}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Example 10. Referred to the Figure 10.

Figure 10. Referred to the Example (10)

Theorem 11. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperStarStyles-IV don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (1.24, 1.24, 1.24) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i))| \\
 & V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' : \\
 & T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k} \\
 & I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k} \\
 & \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k} \\
 & V_{i=1,4,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4,5} \in V'' : \\
 & T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k} \\
 & I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \quad V_{i=3,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5-6} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \quad V_{i=4,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=4,5-6} \in V'' : \\
& T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
& \quad V_{i=1,6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,6} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
& \quad V_{i=3,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,4} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
& \}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Example 11. Referred to the Figure 11.

Figure 11. Referred to the Example (14)

Theorem 12. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperStarStyles-V don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} T(V_i), \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} I(V_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-6}\}} F(V_i) \right| \\
 & = (1.21, 1.21, 1.21) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 & \quad V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=1,4,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4,5} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=3,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5-6} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I'_V(E_k) &\sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
\text{and } F'_V(E_k) &\sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
V_{i=4,5-6} &\in V'', \forall V_{j=4,5-6} \in V'' : \\
T'_V(E_k) &\sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
I'_V(E_k) &\sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
\text{and } F'_V(E_k) &\sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k'} \\
V_{i=1,6} &\in V'', \forall V_{j=1,6} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T'_V(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
I'_V(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
\text{and } F'_V(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
V_{i=3,4} &\in V'', \forall V_{j=3,4} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
T'_V(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
I'_V(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
\text{and } F'_V(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
&\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
&\}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Example 12. Referred to the Figure 12.

Figure 12. Referred to the Example (14)

Theorem 13. *Neutrosophic SuperHyperStarStyles-VI don't coincide.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-7}\}} T(V_i), \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-7}\}} I(V_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1,3-4,5-7}\}} F(V_i) \right) \left. \right| \\
 & = (1.44, 1.44, 1.44) = \\
 & = \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 & \quad V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=1,4,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4,5} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
 & \quad V_{i=3,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5-6} \in V'' : \\
 & \quad T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& V_{i=4,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=4,5-6} \in V'' : \\
& T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& V_{i=3,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5-7} \in V'' : \\
& T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& V_{i=4,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=4,5-7} \in V'' : \\
& T'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& I'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k}, \\
& V_{i=1,6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,6} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& T'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& I'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
& V_{i=1,7} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,7} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& T'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& I'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\
& V_{i=6,7} \in V'', \forall V_{j=6,7} \in V'' :
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& T'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& I'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\
& \text{and } F'_V(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\
& \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}
\end{aligned}$$

$$V_{i=3,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,4} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}$$

}

□

Example 13. Referred to the Figure 13.

Figure 13. Referred to the Example (14)

Theorem 14. Neutrosophic SuperHyperStarStyles-VII don't coincide.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-7}\}} T(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-7}\}} I(V_i), \\ & \sum_{V_i \in V' = \{V_{i=1-7}\}} F(V_i))| \\ & = (1.67, 1.67, 1.67) = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \max_{V'' \subseteq V_{SHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V''} F(V_i)) |$$

$$V_{i=1,3,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3,5} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$V_{i=1,4,5} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,4,5} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$V_{i=3,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5-6} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$V_{i=4,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=4,5-6} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$V_{i=3,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,5-7} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$V_{i=4,5-6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=4,5-7} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_k) \sim_{\text{NOT DEFINED}} \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \notin E_k},$$

$$V_{i=1,6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,6} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}$$

$$V_{i=1,6} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,7} \in V'' :$$

$$T'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) =$$

$$\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}$$

$$V_{i=6,7} \in V'', \forall V_{j=6,7} \in V'' :$$

$$\begin{aligned} T'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\ I'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\ \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \end{aligned}$$

$$V_{i=3,4} \in V'', \forall V_{j=3,4} \in V'' :$$

$$\begin{aligned} T'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\ I'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\ \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \end{aligned}$$

$$V_{i=2} \in V'', \forall V_{j=1,3-7} \in V'' :$$

$$\begin{aligned} T'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\ I'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1}, \\ \text{and } F'_{V'}(E_1) &= (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) \not\leq (0.23, 0.23, 0.23) = \\ &\min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_1} \\ &\} \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 14. Referred to the Figure 14.

Figure 14. Referred to the Example (14)

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